

Positioning Vibe Researching in Software Engineering: Dual Perspectives from Junior and Senior Researchers

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Abstract

Vibe coding has emerged as a fashionable practice since early 2025, shifting developers' attention from pure code production toward comprehensive capabilities, through collaboration with artificial intelligence (AI). Alongside such a trend, a related notion, *vibe researching* has appeared in gray literature, referring to a co-research approach of conducting research with AI. Although no empirical studies have examined this phenomenon, as it is a very new concept, an increasing number of software engineering (SE) researchers are utilizing AI in various research stages in increasingly diverse ways, far beyond the language enhancement roles typically acknowledged in recent papers' AI declaration. It raises the need for up-to-date methodological guidance to mitigate AI hallucinations and remain academically rigorous and sustainable in SE research. In this position paper, we illustrate two empirical practices towards the *vibe researching* approach, discussing challenges from both junior and senior researchers' perspectives, and proposing a framework for our SE community.

Keywords: vibe researching; software engineering research; research methodology.

1 Introduction

Vibe coding was first coined in February 2025 by Andrej Karpathy [4], a computer scientist at Tesla, who described it as a new fashionable style of coding by typing prompts. In his post, Karpathy claimed that he even forgot the existence of coding when fully giving into the vibes. As an extension of the *vibe* concept, another term *vibe researching* brings such fashion to academia. Besides several posts on LinkedIn [12] and blogs [14, 18, 2] on *vibe research* or *vibe researching*, the most attention one is a one-hour YouTube video [1], featuring OpenAI's Chief Scientist, Jakub Pachocki, and Chief Research Officer, Mark Chen. Released on September 25th, 2025, the episode garnered over 22 thousand views within the first three weeks, stating that *vibe researching* has come after *vibe coding*.

As a brand-new term, *vibe researching* has not yet been examined empirically in terms of its definition, characteristics, and practices. Nevertheless, insights can be drawn from the emerging body of

studies on *vibe coding*. Through reviewing gray and white literature, Ray [20] positioned *vibe coding* as a transformative paradigm in modern development, going beyond token-level autocomplete to employ multi-agent pipelines, Retrieval-Augmented Generation, and dynamic context management to autonomously scaffold entire projects.

Since *vibe coding* has already become known and practiced among practitioners, Sarker and Drosos [21] conducted an exploratory analysis of five videos selected from a pool of 35 from YouTube and Twitch recordings, each containing rich think-aloud reflections during *vibe coding* sessions. By deeply analyzing more than eight hours of video data, they argue that *vibe coding* differs from previous generations of AI-assisted programming, as prompting takes on a new character in *vibe coding*; also, developers spend more time on acceleration of code generation in AI-assisted programming, while focusing more on orchestrating the models and tools within a complex development environment in *vibe coding*. Drawing on more triangulated data sources, Pimenova et al. [19] characterize what *vibe coding* is through interviews, Reddit threads, and LinkedIn posts. They defined *vibe coding* as *a new paradigm for natural language programming that involves a high level of conversational interaction and co-creation with AI*; the developers' experience through *vibe coding* is characterized by flow and joy.

Most of the existing empirical research on *vibe coding* mentioned above mainly focused on experienced developers. For example, Sarker and Drosos's [21] think-aloud reflections analysis is fully based on experienced coders, and none of the selected videos depict non-programmers; ten out of eleven interviewees in Pimenova et al.'s [19] study are with 4 to 46 years of programming experience. However, it impacts individuals without formal programming training more broadly and in a complex manner. High school students assume *vibe coding* as the default way of coding [1]; *vibe coding* brings socioeconomic impacts, democratizing software engineering [7], but also accelerating the displacement of entry-level programmers and their growth [10].

Building upon emerging insights into *vibe coding*, this position paper presents the definition and challenges of *vibe researching* from the dual perspectives of senior and junior researchers. **Calling for a methodological level discussion of *vibe researching*, we aim to foster transparency in reporting collaboration with AI in software engineering research and connect researchers with diverse levels of experience.**

2 AI-assisted Researching and Vibe Researching

When involving AI in research activities, most studies use the term *AI-assisted researching* [13, 22]; in one post on Medium, it is also called as *deep-research* [2]. As indicated in such a name, AI tools serve as an assistant while researchers are the ones who make all decisions. In *AI-assisted researching*, one significant characteristic is the acceleration of the research process, saving time and reducing workload [13, 2]. Differently, in *vibe researching* AI agents can coordinate and execute the research workflow autonomously [2], which is its key characteristic. In Table 1, we illustrate the differences between *AI-assisted researching* and *vibe researching*, in which researching mainly refers to publication- and scientific knowledge-oriented activities, excluding tasks such as supervision or funding application. Besides positioning AI as a co-researcher rather a tool, *vibe researching* requires boarder and more holistic competences from researchers, as well as a more rigorous methodological report of AI involvement.

In this position paper, we defined *vibe researching* as follows:

Vibe researching is a scientific methodology in which research design, process, and outcomes are co-generated with AI, such that without AI, the findings and knowledge could neither be reproduced nor validated.

3 Dual Perspectives in Vibe Researching

We present how *vibe researching* impacts accordingly across levels of research experience and brings concerns and challenges, drawing on two empirical cases in software engineering. The first one focuses

Table 1: Comparison between *AI-assisted researching* and *vibe researching*

	AI-assisted researching	Vibe researching
Also known as	Deep-research	Vibe-research
Role of AI	Tool	Collaborator and co-researcher
Core characteristic	Acceleration of certain research processes	Co-generation of research and knowledge
Researchers' required skills	Academic expertise and AI tool proficiency	Academic expertise, principal investigator capability, and AI literacy (prompting engineering)
AI Declaration requirements	Stating the tool's name and purpose is sufficient	Need to describe in detail how AI participates in each step and its contribution

on how AI could conduct screening, extracting, and coding stages of systematic literature review (SLR), as junior researchers. The second example shows how senior researchers utilize AI to co-organize a workshop and co-generate the workshop report.

3.1 Vibe Researching for Junior Researchers

SLR is typically the first step for a junior researcher to initiate an academic career and gain an in-depth understanding of a specific research topic through a rigorous methodological process. Recent work by Mäntylä et al. [15, 16, 9] examines how AI can perform as a junior researcher in SLR; these studies were based on GPT 3.5, whose capability is equal to or beyond that of average master students.

In Mäntylä et al.'s serious studies, they evaluate using AI for three stages of SLR, namely the screening, data extraction, and data synthesis processes. Besides the unsurprising speed difference, they compared the accuracy of AI with that of junior researchers, including master's students, doctoral researchers, and postdoctoral researchers. As a preliminary result, GPT 3.5 performs similarly to a master-level student. They conclude that AI can get 80% to 95% SLR-related tasks correct, but also suggest that the researchers should be experts to recognize the 5-20% incorrect ones.

According to the rapid advancement of AI-related technologies, we assume that with GPT 4.0 and upgraded models, and orchestrating multiple AI agents together, AI could do greater and more accurate SLR-related tasks. In this regard, junior researchers are encountering the following challenges in *vibe researching*:

Hard to publish literature review results. It could be quite acceptable for senior communities to collaborate with AI to generate all kinds of literature reviews; however, the manual reviewing remains an essential and valuable journey for junior researchers. To the best of our knowledge, most of the software engineering and information systems top journals do not accept pure reviewing manuscripts anymore. The junior researcher spends years generating an SLR study, but cannot be recognized by publishing it. It raises the question of how juniors can grow up towards seniors without systematically reviewing others' research, and how their reviewing work gains recognition without publishing.

Unconsciously misled by AI errors. As stated by Mäntylä et al. [16], junior researchers hardly recognize the incorrect information generated by AI; so that you can use AI to do research only if you are experts. However, it is not practical - nor desirable - to forbid junior researchers from engaging AI technologies, as it is contradict the principle of technological equality [24]. Without methodological guidance in using AI in *vibe researching*, junior researchers may accept incorrect outputs generated by AI as valid, or spend a lot of effort on validating them. Although our whole communities all face AI hallucinations [11], junior researchers serve more than seniors for a long period before they gain enough experience.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the AIAndAgileXP2025GPT interface generated by workshop organizers.

3.2 Vibe Researching for Senior Researchers

While AI has brought urgent challenges for junior researchers, the seniors seem to be more bold and outspoken when embracing *vibe researching*. Senior researchers have gained enough expertise in research as well as principal investigator capability, presented in Table 1, while another new thing for them is mainly AI literacy and prompt and tool strategies, which are naturally easy to acquire for software engineering people.

Five European software engineering senior researchers and practitioners collaborated with AI, organizing a full-day workshop on AI and Agile at the 26th International Conference on Agile Software Development (XP 2025) [8, 23, 25]. To demonstrate the practical application of the workshop's theme, they co-organized the entire workshop with AI, representing a *vibe researching* instance. Specifically, they prepared the workshop content (the theme song, slides, and images) with Suno.com, GPT-o4-mini model, Gamma.app, and Flux Fast 1.1 model; they analyzed the workshop data using Gemma 3 27B model and GPT-4o model; furthermore, they summarized and reported the workshop knowledge by working together with Gemini 2.5 Pro model, a customized knowledge base created on GPT-4o model. From both on-site participants' discussion and organizers' reflection, the key lessons learned from using AI focus on *AI literacy*, *prompting strategies*, and *cross-checking different AI tools* [8]. Notably, in addition to the traditional workshop report, the trained AI portal in Figure 1 also represents a key research outcome.

Such detailed experience reporting of organizing a workshop with AI can be a vivid example of how senior researchers conduct research activities towards *vibe researching* approach. However, more critical concerns are from seniors as well, which are more from the perspective of a sustainable software engineering community.

Epistemic conservatism and authority amplification. Experts are usually confident in their own long-cultivated research methods and scientific knowledge. Such confidence makes them highly sensitive to any sign of unreliability and potential sloppiness in research activities. When they notice any mistake generated by AI, it may increase their hesitation to deeply embrace *vibe researching*. More importantly, the community tends to easily buy into senior researchers' research output without much criticism. If seniors utilize AI in research without methodological level reporting and validating the results, the wrong knowledge could rapidly spread in the whole community of such a domain.

Increasing Peer-Review Pressure. AI has accelerated the speed of manuscript generation to an unprecedented level. If *vibe researching* becomes a scientific approach, where AI acts as a co-researcher,

the volume of submissions will increase exponentially. As a result, tremendous pressure and workload fall into the peer-review ecosystem, particularly on the senior researchers. Some disciplines have begun to explore using AI for peer review [6, 17]; however, in software engineering, most publishers currently prohibit reviewers from uploading manuscripts to any AI platforms [3, 5]. As the number of AI-involved manuscripts rises and peer-review workload becomes heavier, the overall quality and reliability of accepted publications may be difficult to guarantee.

4 Vibe Researching Positioning Framework

Building upon the aforementioned definition of *vibe researching*, as well as its preliminary empirical examples and challenges from the view of junior and senior researchers. We further propose a positioning framework of *vibe researching* as the following three principles:

(1) AI agents act as mediators in *vibe researching*, bridging junior and senior researchers. AI is not only a toolkit, but more importantly, serves as a mediator that bridges experience, knowledge, and methodological gaps between junior and senior researchers.

(2) Trained AI agents as research outputs in *vibe researching*. Beyond manuscripts, AI agents that are specifically trained or customized for certain research, such as conversational agents, analytical assistants, or domain-specific reasoning models, should also be recognized as legitimate research outputs. Reproduction and validation of such AI agents need to be considered in the following studies.

(3) AI agents triangulation in *vibe researching*. To minimize single-model bias, at least two distinct AI agents should be employed in each research stage to form triangulated validation. The transparent and clear reports of which and how AI agents are involved need to be reported in manuscripts.

5 Conclusions

This positioning paper presented the definition, empirical practices, challenges for junior and senior researchers, and principles of the *vibe researching* approach, bringing AI-involved research activities into a methodological-level discussion. Our software engineering community will benefit from adopting *vibe researching* as a scientific method, aligning with AI advancements, empowering researchers, and remaining academically rigorous and sustainable.

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